

Workshop: Designing for Happiness: A workshop about symbolic meaning

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Topic Research on happiness argues that material possessions have a limited impact on happiness [1, 2], and that engaging in certain activities is a more effective approach [3, 4]. Accordingly, experience-enabling products have been deemed useful for increasing happiness [5, 6, 7]. We propose that, in addition to experience-enabling products, certain material possessions that hold significant narratives can similarly be a valid way to support happiness. In that sense, the symbolic meaning of products can have a role in designing for happiness. Symbolically meaningful possessions allow the re-consumption of experiences (souvenirs) [8], represent relationships [9], help communicate one's identity [10], and provide an anchor for meaningful narratives (heirlooms) [11]. Designing with symbolic meaning represents an opportunity for design because it can potentially increase the relevance of products, result in higher quality interactions and encourage subjective well-being. Previous research [12] identified six happiness-related symbolic meanings in products, based on Ryff's model of psychological well-being [13]: positive relations with others, personal growth, purpose in life, environmental mastery, autonomy, and self-acceptance. The six meanings were used to develop 16 design directions to inspire designers to create products that are predisposed for symbolic meaning attribution, and therefore can have an impact on users' happiness [14].

Purpose Happiness is a universally desirable human goal. Drawing from research on Positive Psychology, Positive Design focuses on individual well-being and on the opportunities for design to contribute to an improvement towards positive states of feeling and being. The workshop aims to communicate research on Positive Design (design for happiness) and to disseminate a tool that can help designers create products that are predisposed for symbolic meaning attribution. This approach is expected to generate an improved interaction with products, which can result longer user-product relations and generate a positive impact in the happiness of users.

Keywords *Symbolic meaning, Positive design, Happiness, Design tool, Design workshop*